

Responsible Neurotechnology: ABDN's Response to UNESCO's Draft Recommendation on the Ethics of Neurotechnology

Executive Summary

This is the African Brain Data Network's (ABDN) response to the Global consultation on the first draft of the UNESCO Recommendation on the Ethics of Neurotechnology. It covers the provisions or points we agree with and wish to amplify; the identifiable gaps and some critical issues that should be added to the Recommendation.

Highlights

- We agree with the Ad Hoc Expert Group (AHEG) that prepared the Recommendation that seeks to integrate diverse perspectives, especially voices from underrepresented communities as a means of ensuring epistemic justice (section IV.2.6). This is critical because neurotechnology like other emerging technologies is not value-neutral but value-laden. Eke (2024) highlights this as a lesson to be learnt from AI ethics. The inclusion of the philosophy of *Ubuntu* in section III.2 (n.24) gives hope to us as Africans.
- We agree with the combined governance approach taken by the Recommendation: value-based approach, rights-based approach and risk-based approach (section IV). The combination of these approaches helps to incorporate critical characteristics of a fuzzy and emerging technology like neurotechnology, particularly as it converges more with other technologies like AI.
- We agree with the Recommendation's provision for neural and cognitive biometric data to be given special recognition in the law (section V.4 n. 161). This is in recognition of the exceptionalism of this type of data. A discussion that was explored in Hallinan et al., (2023).

Gaps and Issues

However, there are identifiable **gaps and issues**.

- Neural data is defined as “quantitative data about the structure, activity and function of the nervous system of a living organism” (section II.1 no. 7). We believe that neural data can also be

qualitative. These include; Detailed descriptions of human behaviours during experiments, such as movement patterns, facial expressions, or vocalisations, often linked to neural activity, first-person accounts or self-reports of experiences, sensations, emotions, or perceptions, collected through interviews, annotations by researchers or clinicians on neuroimaging data (e.g., fMRI, PET scans) or electrophysiological recordings (e.g., EEG, EMG, MEG), describing observed patterns, anomalies, or noteworthy features, as this will ensure a broader and more inclusive understanding that benefits diverse research methodologies.

- In section II.2 no. 11, the use of the word ‘mental activities’ is vague. This requires a more detailed explanation or a definition.
- The Recommendation observed that materials that are used for neurotechnology can be difficult to mine and the process is harmful to the environment (e.g., lithium used for batteries). This is very important. However, it did not mention nor address the issue of labour exploitation that happens in this process. Extending this discussion to include social impacts, particularly labour practices, could provide a more holistic view of the ethics in sourcing materials.
- Again in section II.2 no. 14, the Recommendation states that animal research and data are beyond its scope. This is curious given the possibilities of ethics dumping in this case. This is a major topic for Africa given the lack of equivalent international standards for animal welfare in some countries. Eke et al., (2023) explored this in detail.
- The Recommendation was indeed right to emphasise the importance of consent and autonomy in section IV.2.3. No. 75 as well as in sections V.1.5. And V. 2. However, what it failed to point out is the possibility of collective right to privacy and collective responsibility in Africa.¹ Whereas this might be the reality in the Global North, it is a live debate in the Global South.
- In section IV.2.4 no. 78, the Recommendation listed four elements of trustworthiness required for neurotechnology. We will suggest that *robustness* be added to the list. Trustworthiness should also be measured with how robust the technology is to deal with errors or inconsistencies during the whole life cycle phases of neurotechnology. As Africans who understand the colonial tendencies or coloniality in emerging technologies, *decoloniality* is a principle that should be added too. For neurotechnology to be trustworthy for Africans, it should demonstrate that it has taken steps to mitigate against *coloniality* (in data, in algorithms and in resources).
- In many parts of the Recommendations, critical issues such as consent, privacy as well as specific issues related to children, older people and people living with disability were duly mentioned. However, an issue that did not receive any attention is the issue of *incidental findings*, particularly in research and consumer products. This deserves a small attention because stakeholders involved in consumer products might not be fully aware of the responsibilities involved.
- We suggest that following the Recommendation, UNESCO should establish a Neurotechnology Incident Database dedicated to indexing the collective history of harms or near harms realised in

¹ <https://researchictafrica.net/wp/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Data-Trusts-Concept-Note.pdf>

the real world by the design, development and deployment of neurotechnology. This can help to make a case for effective regulation in certain countries.

- The recommendation in Section V5 No. 168 rightly mentioned equity, consent, individual and community autonomy, and the nature of enhancement itself as crucial concerns that should be considered with the use of Enhancement/ Augmentation neurotechnologies but failed to recognise potential challenges that could arise from long-term widespread use of such technologies such as the issue of co-dependency of end users on the technologies and its potential effects on human social interactions. For example, individuals with enhancements might communicate or process information in ways that differ significantly from those without enhancements, potentially leading to misunderstandings or feelings of alienation. This technological divide could worsen existing social inequalities and foster new forms of discrimination and bias.

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About African Brain Data Network (ABDN)

ABDN is a network of stakeholders from academia, industry, policy and funding working together to facilitate the responsible generation, processing, sharing, and use of African brain data for research and innovation. The Network seeks to make African brain data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) and ensure that a sufficient number of experts are trained on the use of novel technical tools to collect, process, and apply these datasets. From neuroimages, electrophysiological and anatomical data to behavioural data, this network hopes to make different modalities, disease types from multiple and non-animal organisms available and lead the African neuroscience ecosystem into the era of big data analysis.

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References

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